

ANALYSIS OF CELLO WORKS IN THE WORKS OF

D.D.Shostakovich¹

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Abstract: D.D. Shostakovich made a huge contribution to world musical culture, creating compositions in a variety of genres. A significant niche in his legacy is occupied by chamber-instrumental works for various instruments. Compositions for cello created by D.D. Shostakovich, represent a bright page in the history of cello art and are universally recognized pinnacles of cello literature. The article provides a genre review of the composer's cello works through the prism of interests and content aspects of his work.

Key words: cello art of the 20th century, D.D. Shostakovich, cello sonata, Cello concertos.

The personality and creativity of D.D. Shostakovich is the brightest phenomenon in the world musical culture of the 20th century. He wrote works of various genres: compositions for musical theatre, symphonies, chamber instrumental and vocal music, concertos for instruments, choral opuses, music for films. The composer also contributed to the development of cello performance in the 20th century. Works for cello, created by the master of Russian music, are now included in the repertoire of cellists around the world, are an obligatory part of the programs at international competitions.

It should be noted that the cello is one of those stringed orchestral instruments whose figurative, artistic and technical potential was truly revealed relatively late. More P.I. Tchaikovsky, who highly appreciated the timbre of the instrument, bitterly stated that "the virtuoso prosperity of the cello is coming to its last phase of decline".

Fortunately, the composer's prophecy did not come true, and a few years later, the situation changed dramatically: we can say that the 20th century was the "golden age" of cello performance. This is due, first of all, to the fact that outstanding virtuosos appear on world stages, such as G. Cassado, M. Marechal, A. Navarra, G. Pyatigorsky, P. Fournier, S. Knushevitsky, D. Shafran, and, of course, P. Casals and M.L. Rostropovich.

For musicians of such talent, a repertoire of a new level was needed, which activated the creative thought of composers all over the world. As aptly

emphasized by M.S. Weinberg, the authors of the 20th century had a happy “awakening of the instincts of cello thinking” .

The result of such processes was the appearance of more than a thousand works of the concert genre for cello, including chamber opuses - sonatas, suites, variations, sonatas-rhapsodies, poems .

Some contemporaries of D.D. Shostakovich testified that he called the cello one of his favorite instruments, see about this, although we did not find direct statements from the composer. His interest manifested itself in his youth - as a student he wrote three pieces for cello and piano (op. 9, 1923-24), which were first performed on March 20, 1925 in a joint concert by D.D. Shostakovich and Viktor Yakovlevich Shebalin in the Small Hall of the Moscow Conservatory . In this series, we note another composition of that period - Piano Trio No. 1 (op. 8, 1923), where bright timbre finds are found - cello themes-monologues (for example, the episode before the side part in the exposition of 1 movement), which became the forerunner of intense philosophical cello monologue themes that fill the mature symphonies of the master. In our opinion, the interest in the instrument is also due to the following circumstance. As you know, in addition to composing talent, D.D. Shostakovich was an excellent virtuoso pianist. He often performed at concert venues both solo and in an ensemble with such famous musicians as V.L. Kubatsky, Arnold Ferkelman, A.Livshits and others, replaying a large number of classical chamber-instrumental music. Such creative collaboration became a possible impetus for the creation of the Sonata for Cello and Piano (op. 40, 1934). D.D. Shostakovich dedicated it to the first virtuoso performer V.L. Kubatsky, who made his own version of the cello part. At the same time, the composer's appeal to the chamber genre is in line with his turn to "pure" instrumental music, which can be traced in the work of the mid-1930 years.

First of all, D.D. Shostakovich emphasized the need to work in the field of chamber music, agreeing with contemporaries' discussions about the search for "greater clarity, naturalness, ease of perception." This, perhaps, was reflected in the musical language of the Cello Sonata, which differs significantly from the previous compositions of D.D. Shostakovich (for example, the opera The Nose, the ballet Bolt, etc.). The Sonata for Cello and Piano is the most romantic composition of this period, and, perhaps, of the entire work of D.D. Shostakovich, which opens the door to the world of his soul, thanks to elegiac melancholy, penetrating lyricism. In the composer's biography, researchers find such a curious fact that partly explains the reasons for the romantic structure of this opus - 28-year-old Dmitry Dmitrievich wrote it after a conflict and a temporary

break in relations with his first wife, Nina Varzar. It is difficult to judge how much this episode of his personal life influenced the figurative structure of the content of the sonata, but its lyrical pages, interspersed with outbursts of either anger or bitter irony, testify to the coincidence of romantic aesthetics with the emotional state of the composer. The premiere of the sonata for cello and piano took place on December 25, 1934 at the Leningrad Philharmonic in a brilliant performance by the ensemble V.L. Kubatsky D.D.Shostakovich. The composition was immediately highly appreciated and soon sounded throughout Soviet Union as well as on foreign venues performed by such masters as Mstislav Rostropovich, Daniil Shafran, Gregor Pyatigorsky, Pier Fournier and others.

Two cello concertos, written by the composer already within the framework of the mature period of his creative work, are the pinnacle works of cello literature of the 20th century. They are distinguished by the synthesis of classical traditions and a bright innovative beginning, manifested in the demonstration of new technical capabilities of the solo instrument, the symmetry of the genre, the originality of the dramatic idea with its sharply conflicting clash of the forces of "good" and "evil".

The composer told the first concerto in one of his interviews: "My next major work will be a concerto for cello and orchestra. The concert, apparently, will be three-part. It is difficult for me to say anything definite about its content. I can only say that this concert was conceived relatively long ago; The initial impetus for his composition was his acquaintance with Sergei Prokofiev's symphony-concerto for cello and orchestra. This work interested me and made me want to try my hand at this genre. The concerto was written in a very short time - literally in three months. As you know, the master dedicated the concerto to M.L. Rostropovich, with whom he had creative and friendly relations. The cellist about the composition of D.D. Shostakovich did not immediately recognize: "Once Nina told me: "Slava, if you want him to write music for the cello, never ask him about it!" <...> I learned from the newspapers that Shostakovich was writing a cello concerto. I was crushed because I thought he had found another cellist. It didn't even occur to me that my friend and teacher wouldn't admit to me that he was writing a concerto for me, because he was embarrassed and wasn't sure that I would like this music!" Upon learning that D.D. Shostakovich completed the concert, M.L. Rostropovich immediately arrived from Moscow. The composer played him an opus on the piano, after which he asked: "Tell me, Slava, do you like this music?" And, having heard the answer (Rostropovich recalled that he yelled with delight!), He said: "Thank God. So I can write a dedication for you." "All 117 cello works," the cellist noted, "of which I was the

first performer, are dedicated to me. But none of the authors asked my permission - only Shostakovich”.

The romantic cello of the sonata was revealed in the First Cello Concerto as an instrument expressing the intensity of the tragedy in the hero's soul. By semantic content The figurative world of the work embodies the romantic idea of “two worlds” – here there is a sphere of the lyrical hero, revealing his contradictory spiritual world, and a countersphere, personifying the cruel society in which the hero is forced to stay and fight. The artistic idea of the First Cello Concerto, which is based on a psychological drama and a life-affirming beginning, approaches the semantic concept of the 5th symphony. It should be noted that the composer "breaks" the traditional framework of the genre and writes a 4-part cycle (approaching the symphony genre), where the cadenza becomes an independent part. The composer interprets the role and functions of the symphony orchestra in his own way - he chooses the chamber composition, excluding the group of brass instruments, except for the horn, which is entrusted with the role of the "double" of the soloist .

The second cello concerto was written by D.D. Shostakovich six years later, in the spring of 1966. Its premiere took place on September 25 of the same year - on the day of the composer's 60th birthday - in the Great Hall of the Moscow Conservatory, performed by M.L. Rostropovich and the USSR State Symphony Orchestra conducted by E. Svetlanov. The mournfully elegiac first part of the concert, according to a number of researchers, is an emotional reaction to the news of the death of the poetess A.A. Akhmatova (she passed away on March 5, 1966), whom D.D. Shostakovich called "the queen of Russian poetry". The theme of death is a cross-cutting one for the concerto, the conflict of which lies in the clash of the categories of Good and Evil, the collapsing and crushing hero. D.D. Shostakovich himself later noted that the Second Cello Concerto is "something like the 14th symphony with a solo cello part." In this regard, it is appropriate to recall that the Fourteenth Symphony was written under the influence of M.P. Mussorgsky's Songs and Dances of Death, which the composer orchestrated in 1962. Thus, the works are combined into a single intertextual series, revealing the theme of a person's encounter with death.

Summing up some results, we emphasize that interest in the cello manifested itself already at the first tests of the pen by D.D. Shostakovich, later embodied in the sonata and two Cello Concertos, which became the pinnacles of the cello performing art of the 20th century, reflecting the evolution of the genre and demonstrating the brilliant possibilities of the instrument in revealing serious, large-scale themes of art.

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